

An Analysis of the Influence of Gender and Age on Post-COVID Tourist Preferences in the Hospitality Industry

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Abstract: The study aims to investigate how gender and age affect post-COVID tourists' preferences in the hospitality industry. A quantitative study was conducted, and data were collected through self-administered questionnaires at the Art Centre in Accra, Ghana, between August and September 2025. Purposive and convenience sampling techniques were employed to select respondents. The final data analysis included a total of 387 usable questionnaires. Multivariate and univariate tests were employed to analyse the data collected. SPSS version 26 was the statistical tool used for the analysis. The study revealed that both gender and age differences significantly affect post-COVID tourist preferences in Ghana. It is recommended that the Ghana Tourism Industry and policymakers introduce policies and training programs to support demographic-sensitive tourism planning in relation to their preferences. It is also suggested that managers of tourist destinations strive to identify the pressing needs and desires of the various age groups who patronize tourist destinations. It is also critical for destination managers to develop targeted strategies that enhance tourist satisfaction, encourage repeat visits, and support the sustainable recovery of Ghana's hospitality industry.

Keywords: Age, Gender, Ghana, Hospitality, Tourism, Post-COVID, Tourist Preferences

1. Introduction

The hospitality industry has consistently faced challenges in sustaining business operations, particularly during periods of natural disasters, terrorist attacks, and global health crises (Delafontaine, 2017; Hung & Yuen, 2018). The COVID-19 pandemic, however, has had an especially profound impact on the hospitality and tourism sectors. In response to the crisis, the World Health Organization (WHO) issued preventive guidelines, and governments worldwide implemented stringent measures such as lockdowns, travel restrictions, and social distancing protocols. These interventions, while essential for public health, led to the temporary closure of many hospitality establishments for an unprecedented duration, resulting in a sharp decline in demand across the industry (Bartik et al., 2020; Mamalis, Kamenidou & Stavrianea, 2022).

The restrictions and bans imposed within the travel ecosystem had a profound impact on interconnected industries, with the hospitality sector experiencing the most severe consequences (Alan et al., 2020). The extensive media coverage of the pandemic, emphasizing the rapid rise in infection rates, the expanding geographic spread, and the World Health Organization's (WHO) official declaration of a global pandemic, further intensified public anxiety and uncertainty (Lee et al., 2020). According to data from the UN Secretary-General's Tourism Office, international travel has now nearly returned to pre-pandemic levels, with Africa recovering 92% of its previous visitation figures (Tourism Report, 2023). In Ghana, for instance, domestic visitor numbers, which stood at 669,311 in 2019, declined sharply by 69% in 2020 due to the pandemic's disruptive effects on travel and tourism. However, attraction site visits rebounded to 945,405 in 2022, marking a 49% year-over-year

increase and signaling a gradual recovery from the earlier downturn (Tourism Report, 2023). Hotels within the hospitality sector recorded an average occupancy rate of approximately 44% in 2020, a notable decline from 66% in 2019 (Kwok, 2021). Moreover, the impact of COVID-19 on business travel varied significantly across regions, with North America experiencing a 79% reduction, Western Europe 77%, Latin America 59%, Eastern Europe 63%, and both the Asia-Pacific and the Middle East & Africa regions 52% (Stimson, 2021). These substantial disruptions are expected to prompt a fundamental transformation in the tourism industry's strategic approach (Hall et al., 2020; Gössling et al., 2020). As a result, the sector must undergo a comprehensive reevaluation to demonstrate an exceptional capacity to adapt to travellers' changing preferences, preserve its credibility, and identify emerging tourism demands (Nientied & Shutina, 2020; Wachyuni & Kusumaningrum, 2020).

Borbon and Pulhin (2023) found that gender and age have a significant impact on post-COVID tourist behaviour, revealing that Generation Z and female respondents demonstrated stronger travel preferences. Their study indicated that these groups were more willing to travel internationally once restrictions were lifted, with health risks and vaccine availability emerging as key considerations. Similarly, Asimah, Hurriyati, Gaffar, and Wibowo (2023) identified gender and age as influential factors shaping revisit intentions for the Panafest and Emancipation festivals in Ghana. Their findings showed that male visitors and older individuals were more likely to return, underscoring the importance of demographic variables in shaping post-pandemic tourist behaviour.

Although the studies by Borbon and Pulhin (2023) and Asimah et al. (2023) provide valuable insights into the role of gender and age in specific tourism contexts, they remain limited in scope and do not comprehensively address the broader hospitality industry in Ghana. There remains a clear research gap regarding how gender and age differences influence post-COVID tourist preferences within the hospitality sector and the nature of these evolving preferences in the post-pandemic era. Bridging this gap is essential for developing targeted strategies that enhance tourist satisfaction, promote repeat visitation, and support the sustainable recovery and growth of Ghana's hospitality industry.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Tourist Preference

The key sustainability aspect for any activity's success is satisfied consumers, and tourism is becoming more and more important to both the global economy and the economic growth of many countries. It is essential to comprehend tourists as decision-makers in order to better align local supply with tourist demands and preferences (Frias, Raskova, Costa & Cabral, 2021). Pratama, Hidayanti and Abdul Haji (2023) define tourist preferences as the inclinations and choices of visitors that significantly influence their decisions to visit attractions, specifically highlighting how these preferences impact both tourist attractiveness and the overall decision-making process regarding visits to destinations. The concept of tourist preferences involves compiling expert and consumer assessments of various indicators, including natural, cultural, historic, and socio-economic factors, to evaluate and rank regions based on their tourism potential within a fuzzy information environment (Rzayev & Rzayeva, 2020). Tourist preferences encompass personal characteristics, planned vacation activities, and emotional aspects, influencing decisions on touristic products (Grossmann, Sertkan, Neidhardt, & Werthner, 2023). These preferences are complex and dynamic, requiring destinations to adapt by listening to tourists' varying perceptions and expectations to enhance their overall experience and satisfaction (Arsana, Budi & Sulasmini, 2018).

2.2 Tourists Demographics Variables and Empirical Review Hypothesis Development

To enhance the tourism experience, the key drivers that affect post-COVID tourists' preferences, which include the tourists' demographic variables, need to be investigated. The demographic

variables considered for this study are gender and age, examined from the perspective of the tourism industry in Ghana. Gender and age demographic variables have been used in several studies to investigate how they affect tourists' preferences (Khankova, 2025; Anuar, Farah Syazwani, & Kelvin, 2016; Alkohaiz et al., 2025; Alagöz & Güneş, 2024; Zhangqi, Shan, Xiuyun, & Huating, 2013; Turkson, Amoah, & Van Eyk, 2023; Turkson, Yeboah, Yeboah, & Eleke-Aboagye, 2024) in different contexts, such as shopping malls and tourism. However, these variables have not been investigated from the viewpoint of the Ghanaian tourism industry.

Gender differences influence customers' shopping preferences based on their different needs and lifestyles (Turkson et al., 2024). Since customers differ in taste and preferences (Ahmed, Senthikumar, & Nallusamy, 2018; Turkson et al., 2024), gender differences are proposed to affect post-COVID tourist preferences in Ghana. Khankova (2025) examined gender differences in tourist preferences among young people in the Sverdlovsk region. It was revealed that 35.8% of respondents preferred Europe as a vacation destination, with female respondents favouring it at 24.8% compared to 11.0% for males. Additionally, women are more inclined to use online resources for vacation information (12.3% vs. 7.6%). Similarly, Anuar et al. (2016) found that gender differences had some influence on tourist preferences and the justifiability of destination decisions. The study conducted by Rodríguez-Pallas, Sarabia Molina, Sánchez-Fernández, and Ramón-Cardona (2024) highlights significant gender differences in travel preferences among Spanish consumers of travel agencies, and women tend to favour exploring new destinations, while men show a preference for relaxation-oriented travel. Alkohaiz et al. (2025) posit that tourist women preferred events, festivals, pilgrimages, and family gatherings for domestic tourism, while tourist men favoured affordability, freedom from customs, and forming new friendships in international tourism. Conversely, women showed a greater interest in experiencing different cultures compared to men. Vespestad and Mehmetoglu (2015) indicated that tourist women prioritise mental relaxation, escape, physical activity, and cultural learning, while valuing destination attributes like restaurant options and price more than tourist men. Conversely, men show greater interest in fishing and boating activities. Matalas, Panaretos, Tzoutzou, and Lazaridis (2023) found that women were more inclined to try local cuisine than visiting males, particularly in connection to gaining cultural experience and excitement, fostering interpersonal relationships, and health concerns. In addition, the study showed that females pay more than men to eat at Greek restaurants and bars, as well as inside the amenities at their hostel. Women were also found to be more satisfied than men with their travel meals, and they spent more on food during the pandemic than before. Thus, it can be hypothesized that:

H1: Gender differences affect post-COVID tourist preference in Ghana's hospitality industry

The study of Alagöz and Güneş (2024) revealed significant differences in destination choice factors among generations X, Y, and Z, in terms of infrastructure facilities, access to information, and tourist attractions, indicating that age influences preferences in tourism destination selection. According to Zhangqi, Shan, Xiuyun, and Huating (2013), young tourists (under 35) prefer exploration and amusement, adults (35-45) seek experiences with family, while elderly tourists (over 45) favour nostalgia, relaxation, and historical sites. These age-related preferences significantly influence tourism market segmentation and behaviour. In a survey conducted by the TNS Political and Social network between January 24 and 30, 2013, 30,628 respondents from various social and demographic groups in 27 EU member states, as well as Croatia, Turkey, the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Iceland, Norway, Serbia, and Israel, indicated that wellness, spa, health treatments, destination's nature and culture, were most likely to be cited by respondents aged 55 and over. However, those aged 25 to 54 favour the beach and sun, but those aged 15 to 24 are more likely to claim that a particular event is the primary cause for travelling to a tourist location (European Commission, Brussels, 2014). In another study, Bel, Lacroix, Lyser, Rambonilaza, and Turpin (2015) discovered different tourist groups based on their age and family structure, through the use of activity-based segmentation. It was discovered that "water-based

activities" catered to families with children, "outdoor pursuits" to adults, and "natural and cultural heritage discovery" and "gastronomy" to adults over 50. Thus, it can be hypothesised that:

H2: Age difference significantly affects post-COVID tourist preference in Ghana’s hospitality industry

3. Methodology

Purposive and convenience sampling techniques were employed to select a total of 400 respondents for the study. After data cleaning, 387 valid responses were retained and utilized for quantitative analysis examining the influence of gender and age differences on tourist preferences in the hospitality industry during the post-COVID-19 era. The target population comprised tourists visiting Ghana, with data collected at the Ghana Art Center in Accra. The Ghana Art Center in Accra is a popular destination known for its diverse range of Ghanaian art, crafts, and cultural products such as wood carvings, kente cloth, paintings, beadwork, traditional musical instruments, clothing, jewellery, and home décor. Data were gathered through a structured, self-administered survey questionnaire. Only respondents aged 18 years and above were eligible to participate and were approached upon entering or exiting the Ghana Art Center.

The questionnaire was developed based on previous research studies and consisted of 12 items, two demographic questions (gender and age) and ten statements assessing tourist preferences. The ten preference statements included: *“I prefer destinations that offer a variety of outdoor activities (e.g., hiking, biking, swimming); Cultural experiences (e.g., museums, festivals) are more important to me than relaxation during my travels; I enjoy trying local cuisine and food experiences when I travel; I prioritize visiting historical landmarks and heritage sites over modern attractions; I prefer destinations that are less crowded and off the beaten path; Shopping is an important part of my travel experience; I value eco-friendly and sustainable tourism practices when choosing a destination; I am more likely to return to a destination that offers unique and memorable experiences; I prefer destinations that provide a good balance between adventure and relaxation; Access to technology and Wi-Fi is a critical factor in my travel decisions.”*

Responses were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*). To assess the internal consistency of the instrument, Cronbach’s alpha was computed, yielding a coefficient of 0.891, indicating a high level of reliability. Both multivariate and univariate analyses were conducted to examine the effects of gender and age on tourist preferences in Ghana. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS (Version 26).

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 Profile of the respondents

Table 1 presents the demographic information of the respondents used for the study.

Table 1. Demographic Information

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	287	74.2
	Male	100	25.8
	Total	387	100.0
Age	18 – 27	267	69.0
	28 – 37	63	16.3
	38 – 47	57	14.7
	Total	387	100.0

Source: Researchers’ compilation (2025).

Table 1 reveals a clear demographic distribution among the surveyed population, highlighting a significant gender imbalance and a predominant age group. With 74.2% of respondents identifying as female and only 25.8% as male, this suggests a strong representation of women in the sample. Additionally, the age distribution indicates that the majority of participants are young adults aged 18 to 27, comprising 69% of the total, while those aged 28 to 37 and 38 to 47 represent smaller segments at 16.3% and 14.7%, respectively.

4.2 Multivariate Test

Table 2 presents the results of multivariate tests assessing the overall effects of the intercept, gender, and age on a set of dependent variables. Four test statistics are reported: Pillai's Trace, Wilks' Lambda, Hotelling's Trace, and Roy's Largest Root, each with identical hypothesis degrees of freedom (df = 5), error degrees of freedom (df = 380), and significance levels (p = .000).

Table 2. Multivariate Tests

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.985	5152.793 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.015	5152.793 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	67.800	5152.793 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	67.800	5152.793 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
Gender	Pillai's Trace	.426	56.381 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.574	56.381 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.742	56.381 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.742	56.381 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
Age	Pillai's Trace	.950	1452.887 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.050	1452.887 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
	Hotelling's Trace	19.117	1452.887 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
	Roy's Largest Root	19.117	1452.887 ^b	5.000	380.000	.000
a. Design: Intercept + Sex + Age						
b. Exact statistic						

Source: Researchers' compilation (2025).

For the intercept, the extremely high F-value (5152.793) and p-value (.000) indicate a significant overall effect of the model, suggesting that the dependent variables collectively differ from zero. For Gender, the F-value (56.381) and p-value (.000) across all test statistics demonstrate a significant multivariate effect, meaning gender significantly influences the combined set of dependent variables. Similarly, for age, the F-value (1452.887) and p-value (.000) indicate a strong multivariate effect, suggesting that age also significantly affects the dependent variables collectively. The consistency across all test statistics (Pillai's Trace, Wilks' Lambda, Hotelling's Trace, and Roy's Largest Root) reinforces the robustness of these findings, confirming that both gender and age are significant predictors of the tourism-related preferences examined. Therefore, hypotheses H1 and H2 were accepted.

4.3 Univariate Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

The Tests of Between-Subjects Effects in Tables 3 and 4 provide a univariate analysis of variance (ANOVA) for each dependent variable, breaking down the effects of gender and age on specific tourist preferences.

Table 3. Tests of Between-Subjects Effects (Gender -specific)

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	Male Mean	Female Mean	F	Sig.
Gender	Outdoor activities	17.829	4.30	4.73	16.431	.000
	Cultural experiences	5.991	4.47	4.29	11.802	.001
	Local cuisine and food experiences	2.282	4.67	4.28	16.914	.000
	Historical landmarks and heritage sites	2.470	4.63	4.92	14.175	.000
	Less crowded	6.707	4.63	4.39	12.850	.000
	Shopping	19.050	4.14	4.63	25.759	.000
	Eco-friendly and sustainable tourism practices	2.573	4.16	4.02	14.485	.000
	Unique and memorable experiences	13.012	4.09	4.77	14.809	.000
	Good balance between adventure and relaxation.	2.937	4.47	4.82	6.118	.014
	Access to technology and Wi-Fi	.140	3.74	4.10	.062	.803

Source: Researchers' compilation (2025).

Table 3 details the univariate effects of gender on ten dependent variables related to tourist preferences. Each variable shows the Type III Sum of Squares, mean scores for males and females, F-values, and significance levels. For "Outdoor activities," ($p = .000$) indicates a significant difference, with females (mean = 4.73) rating higher. For "Cultural experiences," p-value ($p = .001$) indicates a significant difference, with males (mean = 4.47) rating slightly higher. "Local cuisine and food experiences" also shows a significant difference ($p = .000$), with males (mean = 4.67) rating higher. For "Historical landmarks and heritage sites," females (mean = 4.92) rate this higher, with a significant value ($p = .000$). "Less crowded" locations are rated slightly higher by males (mean = 4.63), with a significant value ($p = .000$). "Shopping" shows a strong difference ($p = .000$), with females (mean = 4.63) rating it higher. For "Eco-friendly and sustainable tourism practices," males (mean = 4.16) rate is higher than females, with a significant value ($p = .000$). "Unique and memorable experiences" are rated higher by females (mean = 4.77), with a significant value ($p = .000$). Finally, "Good balance between adventure and relaxation" shows a significant difference ($p = .014$), with females (mean = 4.82) rating it higher. However, "Access to technology and Wi-Fi" shows no significant difference ($p = .803$). The effect sizes (based on Type III Sum of Squares) are generally smaller than those for Age, indicating that gender has a moderate influence on these preferences.

These findings suggest that gender differences play a significant role in shaping tourist preferences. Female tourists tend to favour outdoor activities, visits to historical landmarks, shopping, unique travel experiences, and destinations that offer a balanced mix of adventure and relaxation. In contrast, male tourists are more inclined toward cultural experiences, local cuisine, less crowded destinations, and environmentally sustainable practices. Supporting

these results, Anuar, Farah Syazwani, and Kelvin (2016) observed that gender differences influence both tourist preferences and destination choice. Similarly, Alkohaiz et al. (2025) found that female tourists show a stronger preference for domestic tourism activities such as attending events, festivals, pilgrimages, and family gatherings. Conversely, Rodríguez-Pallas, Sarabia Molina, Sánchez-Fernández, and Ramón-Cardona (2024) reported that men tend to prefer relaxation-oriented travel. Furthermore, Matalas, Panaretos, Tzoutzou, and Lazaridis (2023) highlighted that women are often more motivated to sample local cuisines as a means of engaging with cultural experiences and seeking excitement.

Table 4. Tests of Between-Subjects Effects (Age-specific)

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	18–27 years (267) Mean	28–37 years (63) Mean	38–47 years (57) Mean	F	Sig.
Age	Outdoor activities	5.271	4.38	4.90	4.00	4.858	.028
	Cultural experiences	11.080	4.40	4.00	5.00	21.825	.000
	Local cuisine and food experiences	31.902	4.79	4.13	4.00	236.435	.000
	Historical landmarks and heritage sites	7.295	4.59	4.94	5.00	41.860	.000
	Less crowded	4.200	4.59	4.10	5.00	8.047	.005
	Shopping	1.034	4.19	4.81	4.00	1.398	.238
	Eco-friendly and sustainable tourism practices	87.051	4.39	4.03	3.00	490.056	.000
	Unique and memorable experiences	45.111	3.98	4.81	5.00	51.338	.000
	Good balance between adventure and relaxation.	15.841	4.40	4.84	5.00	32.995	.000
	Access to technology and Wi-Fi	75.598	3.58	3.84	5.00	33.568	.000

Source: Researchers' compilation (2025).

Table 4 examines the univariate effects of age on the same dependent variables, with age groups of 18–27 years (n = 267), 28–37 years (n = 63), and 38–47 years (n = 57). For "Outdoor activities," a significant difference exists (p = .028), with the 28–37 age group having a high preference (mean = 4.90). "Cultural experiences" show a strong difference (p = .000), with the 38–47 group rating it higher (mean = 5.00). "Local cuisine and food experiences" has a highly significant difference (p = .000), with the 18–27 group rating it high (mean = 4.79). For "Historical landmarks and heritage sites," the 38–47 group rates it higher (mean = 5.00), with a significant value (p = .000). "Less crowded" locations show a significant difference (p = .005), with the 38–47 group rating it highest (mean = 5.00). "Shopping" shows no significant difference (p = .238), with means of 4.19 (18–27), 4.81 (28–37), and 4.00 (38–47). "Eco-friendly and sustainable tourism practices" has a highly significant difference (p = .000), with the 18–27 group rating it higher (mean = 4.39). "Unique and memorable experiences" shows a significant difference (p = .000), with the 38–47 group rating it higher (mean = 5.00). For "Good balance between adventure and relaxation," the 38–47 group rates it higher (mean = 5.00), with a significant value (p = .000). Finally, "Access to technology and Wi-Fi" shows a significant difference (p = .000), with the 38–47 group rating it higher (mean = 5.00). The Type III Sum of Squares values (e.g., 87.051 for Eco-friendly practices) suggest larger effect sizes for Age compared to Sex, reinforcing Age as a stronger predictor of preference differences.

These findings indicate that age differences have a significant impact on tourism preferences within Ghana's hospitality industry. Tourists aged 38–47 tend to show stronger preferences for cultural experiences, historical landmarks, less crowded destinations, unique experiences, a balanced mix of adventure and relaxation, and access to technology. In contrast, younger tourists aged 18–27 place greater emphasis on local cuisine and eco-friendly practices, while those in the 28–37 age group prioritize outdoor activities. Supporting these results, Alagöz and Güneş (2024) identified notable generational differences in destination choice factors among Generations X, Y, and Z, particularly concerning infrastructure quality, information accessibility, and tourist attractions, which highlights the influence of age on tourism preferences. Similarly, Zhangqi, Shan, Xiuyun, and Huating (2013) found that adults aged 35–45 often seek family-oriented experiences, whereas older tourists (aged 45 and above) prefer nostalgia-driven, relaxing, and historically rich destinations.

5. Conclusion, Recommendation, Limitations, and Future Research Areas

This study examined the influence of gender and age on post-COVID tourist preferences within Ghana's hospitality industry, addressing a critical gap in understanding how demographic factors shape tourism behaviour in a recovering sector. Findings from the multivariate and univariate analyses of between-subject effects revealed significant impacts of both gender and age on various aspects of tourist preferences, as measured using a reliable 10-item Likert-scale questionnaire (Cronbach's alpha = 0.891). Gender-based differences demonstrated distinct behavioral patterns: female tourists exhibited stronger preferences for outdoor activities, historical landmarks and heritage sites, shopping, unique experiences, and destinations offering a balance between adventure and relaxation. Conversely, male tourists placed greater importance on cultural experiences, local cuisine, less crowded destinations, and environmentally sustainable practices. No significant gender differences were observed regarding access to technology and Wi-Fi.

Age-related variations were even more evident. Tourists aged 38–47 showed the strongest preference for cultural experiences, historical landmarks, less crowded destinations, unique experiences, adventure–relaxation balance, and access to technology. Those aged 18–27 emphasized local cuisine and eco-friendly practices, while the 28–37 group prioritized outdoor activities and shopping, although age differences in shopping preferences were not statistically significant. To enhance the post-COVID recovery of Ghana's hospitality industry, stakeholders should adopt targeted strategies aligned with gender- and age-specific preferences. This includes designing gender-sensitive travel packages and tailoring experiences to meet the distinct expectations of different age groups. Managers of tourist destinations should continuously assess and respond to the evolving needs and motivations of diverse visitor segments. Moreover, destination managers, policymakers, and the Ghana Tourism Authority should collaborate to introduce policies and training programs that promote demographic-sensitive tourism planning.

Future research should employ larger and more diverse samples, integrate qualitative and longitudinal approaches, and explore comparative analyses across regions to refine these strategies, ultimately fostering sustainable growth, repeat visitation, and enhanced tourist satisfaction in Ghana's hospitality industry.

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